

A Study on Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Breastfeeding among Mothers of Under 5 Children in Tripura: A Rural Urban ComparisonKaushik Nag¹, Suzanne Lalduhawmi Colney², Anjan Datta³, Snigdha Das⁴¹Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Tripura Medical College & Dr. BRAM Teaching Hospital, Hapania, Agartala, Tripura-799014, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Tripura Medical College & Dr. BRAM Teaching Hospital, Hapania, Agartala, Tripura -799014, India³Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Tripura Medical College & Dr. BRAM Teaching Hospital, Hapania, Agartala, Tripura -799014, India⁴Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy, Tripura Medical College & Dr. BRAM Teaching Hospital, Hapania, Agartala, Tripura -799014, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Snigdha Das

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Abstract:**Background:** Breastfeeding is a basic human activity, vital to infant and maternal health. Despite strong evidences in support of exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of life and awareness, its prevalence has remained low worldwide.**Objective:** The objective of the present study was to compare the knowledge, attitude and practices towards breast feeding and infant feeding practices between urban and rural mothers of under 5 children in Tripura, India.**Methodology:** A cross-sectional study was done in rural field practice area and in the urban field practice area under Department of Community Medicine, Tripura Medical College & Dr. BRAM Teaching Hospital. Data was collected by the researchers through face-to-face interview, by house to house visit. Collected data was compiled and analysed on Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS v.16). P value less than 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.**Results:** The study showed 66.7% mothers had good knowledge about breastfeeding in both urban and rural population. Majority of mothers aged less than 20 years and the highly-educated mothers had a good knowledge about the meaning of exclusive breastfeeding. Majority of the participants had good practice of breastfeeding which was higher among the age group of 20-30 years. There was a positive association between higher socio economic status and mothers having institutional deliveries with breastfeeding practices. Breastfeeding counselling, socio economic status, literacy and age of the mother had a significant influence on breastfeeding patterns and breastfeeding knowledge.**Conclusion:** This study showed approximately two third of the study population had good knowledge on breastfeeding. Educated mothers had more good practice than illiterate mothers. Mothers of urban area had more positive attitude towards breastfeeding compared to mothers of rural area. Awareness about importance of exclusive breastfeeding can enhance knowledge, attitude and practice of breastfeeding among both urban and rural population.**Keywords:** Attitude, Breast feeding, India, Infant, Knowledge, Mothers, Practices.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Breast milk is critical for sustaining newborn infant health and wellbeing. Exclusive Breast Feeding (EBF) is defined as infant feeding with human milk without the addition of any other liquids or solids [1]. The American Academy of Paediatrics Policy Statement on Breastfeeding and the Use of Human Milk has established recommendations for exclusive breastfeeding for a baby's first six months of age [2]. WHO and UNICEF recommend

initiation of breastfeeding within the first hour of life, specifying exclusive breastfeeding at least up to 6 months of age (i.e., the infant only receives breast milk without any additional food or drink, not even water unless there are medical reasons). The mother should breastfeed on demand as often as the child wants, day and night, use of bottles, teats or pacifier and continued breastfeeding up to 2 years of age or beyond, with introduction of

nutritionally adequate and safe complementary (solid) foods at 6 months [3]. Breast feeding is the safest, least allergic and best infant feeding method. It has nutritional, immunological, behavioural and economic benefits and also provide desirable mother infant bonding [4], also it has been seen that babies who are exclusively breastfed for the first six months of age are 11 times less likely to die from diarrhoea and 15 times less likely to die from pneumonia [3].

Breast milk consists of basic nutrients containing proteins, vitamins and carbohydrate. But more importantly, presence of minerals fulfils micronutrient needs and maternal antibodies improves the immune system inhibiting infantile infections like gastrointestinal, respiratory and skin infections and increases physical and neurological growth of the baby. Benefit of breastfeeding for mothers is prevention of post-partum haemorrhage and subsequently maternal mortality reduction, also amenorrhoea due to lactation is a natural contraceptive method for exclusively breast feeding mothers up to a period of first six months. Breast feeding also reduces the incidence of breast cancer and ovarian cancer among mothers, additionally helping in weight reduction i.e., prevention of obesity and subsequently reduction in the burden of cardiac morbidity and mortality [5].

For infants, not being exclusively breastfed is associated with an increased incidence of infectious morbidity, including otitis media, gastroenteritis, and pneumonia, as well as elevated risks of childhood obesity, type 1 and type-2 diabetes, leukemia, and sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS). It has also been seen that among premature infants, not receiving breast milk is associated with an increased risk of necrotizing enterocolitis (NEC). Disadvantages for mothers who fail to breastfeed is associated with an increased incidence of premenopausal breast cancer, ovarian cancer, retained gestational weight gain, type 2 diabetes, and the metabolic syndrome [6].

Although breastfeeding rates are slowly increasing, exclusive breast feeding remain still very low, there is a need for implementation of an educational program through primary health care settings as well mass media to improve, promote and support the exclusive breastfeeding practice [7].

Globally, only 42 per cent of newborns are put to the breast within the first hour of birth, and only 2 in 5 infants less than 6 months of age are exclusively breastfed. The data show that less than three quarters of children aged 12-15 months are still breastfeeding. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that this practice continue until age 2 and beyond, yet less than half of young children aged 20-23 months are benefitting from it [8]. According to NFHS-4 data, initiation of breast-

feeding within one hour of birth in India is only 41.6 per cent even after a tremendous increase in institutional births from 38.7 per cent (2005-06) to 78.9 per cent (2015-16). There has not been any remarkable progress as only a small increment has been recorded in exclusive breastfeeding rates amongst infants 0-6 months of age, from 46.3 per cent (2005-06) to 54.9 per cent (2015-16). Moreover, it is really depressing that the timely complementary feeding rates have gone down from 52.6 per cent (2005-06) to 42.7 per cent (2015-16). The numbers have, however, improved substantially from a 46.4 % in NFHS-3. The latest survey also shows that 56% of the rural children below six months were exclusively breastfed, while it was only 52.1% amongst urban children [9]. While the initiation of breastfeeding indicators shows substantial improvement since NFHS-3, many infants are still deprived of the highly nutritious first milk (colostrum) and the antibodies it contains.

In the state although breastfeeding is nearly universal in Tripura, only 71 percent of children under 6 months are exclusively breastfed. Ninety percent are put to the breast within the first day of life, but only 46 percent started breastfeeding in the first hour of life [10].

A lot of factors ranging from customs, cultural practices, and education of parents, demographic, social, biophysical and psychosocial factors, and support from family and health workers play a role in successful breastfeeding practices as recommended. [11,12] While, a number of studies have assessed knowledge, attitude and practice of breastfeeding in different parts of the world; such studies are limited among Indian mothers. With this background the study was conducted with the aim to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices regarding breast feeding among mothers in a rural and urban area of Tripura.

Methodology:

A community based cross sectional study was conducted among under five mothers attending Madhupur and Dukli training centres under department of Community Medicine, Tripura Medical College & Dr. BRAM Teaching Hospital during the period of April to June 2019. Mothers not found despite of three home visits, suffering from breast cancer, active tuberculosis, AIDS, psychoses, active herpetic lesion on breast, undergoing cancer chemotherapy were excluded from the study. Sample size was calculated by using formulae

$$n = 4pq/l^2 \text{ (where } n = \text{ sample size, } p = \text{ prevalence, } q = 1 - p, l = \text{ allowable error).}$$

The sample size was found to be 83, taking the prevalence of the practice of exclusive breastfeeding in Tripura (70.7%)³ at confidence level of

95% and absolute error (d) of 10% (i.e., $a = 0.1$). Taking 10% as non-response rate, final sample size was found to be 93 ($83 + 83 \times 10\% = 93$). Finally, we interviewed 93 mothers of under five children each from Madhupur and Dukli area. First of all, we collected the list of under-five mothers of Dukli and Madhupur area with the help of family register.

This was the sampling frame for the respective study area i.e., Madhupur and Dukli. Now participants were selected by simple random sampling technique till we reach our desired sample size. A pre-designed and pre-tested, semi-structured interview schedule was used to collect the required information. After obtaining written consent, all mothers were explained about purpose of the study and that they were interviewed at their homes. Data was collected by the researchers through face-to-face interview, by house to house visit in Madhupur and Dukli areas of Tripura. It took approximately 15 minutes to complete the structured schedule.

The collected data was entered and analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 16.0.

Descriptive statistics like mean, median, frequency and percentages of various parameters was calculated. For correct response of knowledge, attitude and practice questions, we have assigned 2 marks and for incorrect response 1 mark was given. We have categorized good and poor knowledge, attitude and practice by median knowledge, attitude and practice score. Participants scoring above median score were categorized as having good knowledge, attitude and practice of breastfeeding and participants scoring below median score were categorized as having poor knowledge, attitude and practice of breastfeeding. Chi-Square test will be used to find association and correlation between breastfeeding with different attributes. The p value <0.05 will be considered significant. The study was conducted after getting the permission from to the Institutional Ethics Committee of Tripura Medical College & Dr. BRAM Teaching Hospital, Hapania, and Agartala.

Results

Sociodemographic characteristics (Table 1)

The present study showed, majority of the study participants (72%) were between 20 to 30 years and 14% each in less than 20 years old, more than 30 years old. The study participants were predominantly housewives (95.7%), Hindu in religion (82.8%), non-tribal (87.1%).

More than half of the mothers belong to Nuclear family (54.8%) in rural area. The present study showed, majority of the study participants (66.7%) were between 20 to 30 years, followed by 20.4%

who were less than 20 years old and 12.9% were more than 30 years. The study participants were predominantly housewives (94.6%), Hindu by religion (88.2%), non-tribal (93.5%). More than half of the population belongs to Nuclear family (52.7%) in urban area. Majority of the mothers were primipara (73.1%) in urban area compared to rural area (54.8%). Urban mothers had higher institutional delivery (95.7%) compared to rural mothers (83.9%). Most of the mothers delivered at term (82.8%) and normal vaginal delivery was the most common mode of delivery (75.3%) in rural area whereas urban mothers had 55.9% normal vaginal delivery followed by caesarean section (24.7%). (Table 2) In rural area, majority of the mothers less than 20 years age (76.9%) had good knowledge and among 20 to 30 years age group, 65.7% mothers had good knowledge whereas among more than 30 years age group mothers, majority (38.5%) had poor knowledge on exclusive breastfeeding (EBF).

This difference of knowledge about breast feeding with age of the participants was not statistical significant. Majority of the mothers less than 20 years age (61.5%) had good practice and among 20 to 30 years age group (71.6%) mothers had good practice whereas among more than 30 years age group mothers, majority (30.8%) had poor practice of exclusive breastfeeding (EBF). This difference of knowledge about breast feeding with age of the participants was not statistical significant. (Table 3 & 4)

In urban mothers, majority of the mothers less than 20 years age (78.9%) had good knowledge and among 20 to 30 years age group, 66.1% mothers had good knowledge whereas among more than 30 years age group mothers, mothers equally (50%) had good knowledge on exclusive breastfeeding (EBF). This difference of knowledge about breast feeding with age of the participants was not statistical significant. Mothers (57.1%) belonging to nuclear family had good knowledge and (77.3%) belonging to joint family had good knowledge whereas (42.9%) of mothers from nuclear family had poor knowledge. Among the interviewed mothers, who were housewives, 61(69.3%) had good practice of EBF, while 27(30.0%) had poor practice and who were working mothers, 4(80%) had good practice while 1(20%) had poor practice. Mothers who were <20 years of age, 16 (84.2%) had good practice of EBF and 3(15.8%) had poor practice. Mothers who were between 20-30 years of age, 32(62.9%) had good practice and 23(37.1%) had poor practice. Mothers who were >30 years, 10(83.3%) had good practice while 2 (16.7%) had poor practice.

Almost one third of the illiterate mothers of rural area (33.3%). had poor practice, whereas all the mothers educated up to graduate and above had

good practice of EBF. The present study shows that as education of mother has increased, the level of good practice of breastfeeding has also increased. There was difference among the attitudes of the mothers of urban and rural areas. Majority

(75.30%) of the mothers of urban area had a good attitude towards breast feeding where as 50.50% of the mothers in rural area didn't have good attitude towards breast feeding their children. (Table 5& 6)

Table 1: Sociodemographic features of under-five mothers of rural and urban area (n=93)

Socio demographic variables		Rural Frequency (%)	Urban Frequency (%)
Age of Mother	<20 years	13 (14)	19 (20.4)
	20-30 years	67 (72)	62 (66.7)
	>30 years	13 (14)	12 (12.9)
Occupation of Mother	Housewife	89 (95.7)	88 (94.6)
	Working	4 (4.3)	5 (5.4)
Type of Family	Nuclear	51 (54.8)	49 (52.7)
	Joint	42 (45.2)	44 (47.3)
Religion of Mother	Hindu	77 (82.8)	82 (88.2)
	Muslim	16 (17.2)	11 (11.8)
Ethnicity	Non-Tribal	81 (87.1)	87 (93.5)
	Tribal	12 (12.9)	6 (6.5)
Education of Mother	Illiterate	3 (3.2)	5 (5.4)
	Upto primary	46 (49.5)	35 (37.6)
	Upto secondary	30 (32.3)	38 (40.9)
	Upto Higher secondary	10 (10.8)	10 (10.8)
	Graduate and above	4 (4.2)	5 (5.4)
Socio-economic Status (BG Prasad 2018)	Upper Class	8 (8.6)	15 (16.1)
	Upper Middle Class	18 (19.3)	23 (24.7)
	Middle Class	26 (28)	29 (31.2)
	Lower Middle Class	25 (26.9)	19 (20.4)
	Lower Class	16 (17.2)	7 (7.5)

Table 2: Obstetric features of under-five mothers of rural and urban area (n=93)

Obstetric variables		Rural Frequency (%)	Urban Frequency (%)
Parity of Mother	Primipara	51 (54.8)	68 (73.1)
	Multi para	42 (45.2)	25 (26.9)
Place of delivery	Home	15 (16.1)	4 (4.3)
	Institutional	78 (83.9)	89 (95.7)
Age gap between children (in years)	<1	2(2.2)	0 (0)
	<2	9 (9.7)	2 (2.2)
	<3	9 (9.7)	3 (3.2)
	>3	21 (22.6)	16 (17.2)
Type of delivery	Term	77 (82.8)	82 (88.2)
	Pre-term	13 (14)	4 (4.3)
	Post-term	3 (3.2)	7 (7.5)
Mode of Delivery	Normal vaginal de- livery	70 (75.3)	52 (55.9)
	LSCS	23 (24.7)	40 (43)
	LSCS	-	1 (1.1)
	Assisted (forceps)	-	-

Table 3: showing association of knowledge about breast feeding of rural mothers with socio demographic characteristics and other factors (n= 93)

Socio demographic characteristics and other factors	Knowledge GOOD	Knowledge POOR	Total	Chi-square value (P value)
Age				
<20years	10 (76.9)	3(23.1)	13(100)	.131(.718)
20-30 years	44 (65.7)	23(34.3)	67 (100)	
>30years	8 (61.5)	5(38.5)	13(100)	
Type of Family				
nuclear	29(56.9)	22(43.1)	51(100)	.799 (.671)

joint	33(78.6)	9 (21.4)	42(100)	
Religion				
Hindu	52(67.5)	25 (32.5)	77 (100)	4.884 (0.027)
Muslim	10(62.5)	6 (67.5)	16 (100)	
Education of mother				
Illiterate	0(0.0)	3(100.0)	3(100.0)	6.889 (0.009)
Upto primary	27(58.7)	19(41.3)	46(100.0)	
Upto secondary	21(70.0)	9(30.0)	30(100.0)	
Upto higher secondary	10(100.0)	0(0.0)	10(100.0)	
Graduate and above	4(100.0)	0(0.0)	4(100.0)	
Social economic status (BG Prasad)				
BG Prasad Cat I	6(75.0)	2(25.0)	8(100.0)	0.782 (0.377)
BG Prasad Cat II	11(61.1)	7(38.9)	18(100.0)	
BG Prasad Cat III	16(61.5)	10(38.5)	26(100.0)	
BG Prasad Cat IV	18(72.0)	7(28.0)	25(100.0)	
BG Prasad Cat V	11(68.8)	5(31.2)	16(100.0)	
Place of delivery				
Home	9 (60.0)	6 (40.0)	15 (100.0)	1.159 (0.885)
Institutional	53 (67.9)	25 (32.1)	78 (100.0)	
Age gap between previous two children				
<1year	1 (50.0)	1(50.0)	2 (100.0)	0.358 (0.550)
<2year	4 (44.4)	5(55.6)	9 (100.0)	
<3year	5 (55.6)	4(44.4)	9 (100.0)	
>3year	16 (76.2)	5(23.8)	21 (100.0)	
NA	36 (69.2)			
Mode of Delivery				
Normal vaginal delivery	44(62.9)	26 (37.1)	70 (100.0)	1.816 (0.403)
LSCS	18(78.3)	5 (21.7)	23 (100.0)	

Table 4: showing association of breast feeding practices of rural mothers with sociodemographic and other obstetric characteristics (n=93)

Socio demographic characteristics and other factors	Good Practices	Poor Practices	Total	Chi-square value (P value)
Occupation of mother				
Housewife	63(70.8%)	26(29.2%)	89(100.0%)	0.786(0.375)
Working	2(50.0%)	2(50.0%)	4(100.0%)	
Age				
<20years	8(61.5%)	5(38.5%)	13(100.0%)	0.531(0.767)
20-30 years	48(71.6%)	19(28.4%)	67(100.0%)	
>30years	9(69.2%)	4(30.8%)	13(100.0%)	
Type of Family				
Nuclear	32(62.7%)	19(37.3%)	51(100.0%)	2.742(0.098)
joint	33(78.6%)	9(21.4%)	42(100.0%)	
Religion				
Hindu	57(74.0%)	28(26.0%)	77(100.0%)	3.634(0.057)
Muslim	8(50.0%)	8(50.0%)	16(100.0%)	
Ethnicity				
Non-tribal	57(70.4%)	24(29.6%)	81(100.0%)	0.068(0.794)
Tribal	8(66.7%)	4(33.3%)	12(100.0%)	
Education of mother				
Illiterate	2(66.7%)	1(33.3%)	3(100.0%)	4.657(0.324)
Upto primary	28(60.9%)	18(39.1%)	46(100.0%)	
Upto secondary	23(76.7%)	7(23.3%)	30(100.0%)	
Upto higher secondary	8(80.0%)	2(20.0%)	10(100.0%)	
Graduate and above	4(100.0%)	0(0,0%)	4(100.0%)	
Parity of mothers				

Primipara	33(64.7%)	18(35.3%)	51(100.0%)	1.444(0.230)
Multi para	32(76.2%)	10(23.85%)	42(100.0%)	
Social economic status (BG Prasad)				0.434(0.980)
BG Prasad Cat I	6(75.0%)	2(25.0%)	8(100.0%)	
BG Prasad Cat II	12(66.7%)	6(33.3%)	18(100.0%)	
BG Prasad Cat III	18(69.2%)	8(30.8%)	26(100.0%)	
BG Prasad Cat IV	17(68.0%)	8(32.0%)	25(100.0%)	
BG Prasad Cat V	12(75.0%)	4(25.0%)	16(100.0%)	
Place of delivery				4.585(0.032)
Home	7(46.7%)	8(53.3%)	15(100.0%)	
Institutional	58(74.4%)	20(25.6%)	78(100.0%)	
Age gap between previous two children				4.907(0.297)
<1year	2(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(100.0%)	
<2year	6(66.7%)	3(33.3%)	9(100.0%)	
<3year	4(44.4%)	5(55.6%)	9(100.0%)	
>3year	17(81.0%)	4(19.0%)	21(100.0%)	
Type of delivery				2.631(0.268)
Term	56(72.7%)	21(27.3%)	77(100.0%)	
Pre-term	8(61.5%)	5(38.5%)	13(100.0%)	
Post-term	1(33.3%)	2(66.7%)	3(100.0%)	

Table 5: showing association of breast feeding knowledge with sociodemographic and other obstetric characteristics of urban mothers (n=93)

Socio demographic characteristics and other factors	Knowledge Good	Knowledge Poor	Total	Chi-square value (P value)
Occupation of mother				.423(0.516)
Housewife	58(65.9)	30(34.1)	88(100)	
Working	4(80)	1(20)	5(100)	
Age of mother				2.798(0.247)
<20years	15(78.9)	4(21.1)	19(100)	
20-30years	41(66.1)	21(33.9)	62(100)	
>30years	6(50)	6(50)	12(100)	
Type of family				4.227(0.040)
Nuclear	28(57.1)	21(42.9)	49(100)	
Joint	34(77.3)	10(22.7)	51(100)	
Religion of mother				2.056(0.358)
Hindu	55(67.1)	27(32.9)	82(100)	
Muslim	7(70)	3(30)	10(100)	
Ethnicity				7.216(0.007)
Non-tribal	61(70.1)	26(29.9)	87(100)	
Tribal	1(16.7)	5(83.3)	6(100)	
Education of mother				4.113(0.391)
Illiterate	5(100)	0(0.0)	5(100)	
Upto primary	21(60)	14(40)	35(100)	
Upto secondary	25(65.8)	13(34.2)	38(100)	
Upto higher secondary	8(80)	2(20)	5(100)	
Graduate & above	3(60)	2(40)	2(40)	
Parity of mother				.438(.508)
Primipara	44(64.7)	24(35.3)	68(100)	
Multipara	18(72.0)	7(28.0)	42(100)	
Socio economic status				6.112(0.191)
BG Prasad cat-I	12(80)	3(20)	15(100)	
BG Prasad cat-II	11(47.8)	12(52.2)	23(100)	
BG Prasad cat-III	20(69)	9(31)	29(100)	
BG Prasad cat-IV	13(68.4)	6(31.6)	19(100)	
BG Prasad cat-V	6(85.7)	1(14.3)	7(100)	

Delivery place				
Home	4(100)	0(0.0)	4(100)	2.090(0.148)
Institutional	58(65.2)	31(34.8)	89(100)	
Age gap between previous two children				1.750(0.626)
<2year	2(100)	0(0.0)	2(100)	
<3year	2(66.7)	1(33.3)	3(100)	
>3year	12(75.0)	4(25)	16(100)	
N/A	46(63.9)	26(36.1)	72(100)	
Type of delivery				.221(0.895)
Term	54(65.9)	28(34.1)	82(100)	
Preterm	3(75)	1(25)	4(100)	
Post term	5(71.4)	2(28.6)	7(100)	
Mode of delivery				0.560(0.756)
Normal vaginal delivery	35(67.3)	17(32.7)	70(100)	
LSCS	26(65)	14(35)	23(100)	

Table 6: showing association of practice of breast feeding with socio demographic characteristics and other factors of urban mothers (n= 93)

Socio demographic characteristics and other factors	Practice Good	Practice Poor	Total	Chi-square value (P value)
Occupation of mother				0.257(.613)
Housewife	61(69.3)	27 (30.7)	88 (100)	
Working	4 (80)	1 (20)	5 (100)	
Age of mother				4.321(.115)
<20years	16 (84.2)	3 (15.8)	19 (100)	
20-30years	39 (62.9)	23 (37.1)	62 (100)	
>30years	10 (83.3)	2 (16.7)	12 (100)	
Type of family				0.013(.911)
Nuclear	34(69.4)	15(30.6)	49(100)	
Joint	31(70.5)	13(29.5)	44(100)	
Religion of mother				2.952(.229)
Hindu	59 (72)	23 (28)	82 (100)	
Muslim	6 (60)	4 (40)	10 (100)	
Christian	0 (0.0)	1 (100)	1 (100)	
Ethnicity				1.206(.272)
Non-tribal	62 (71.3)	25 (28.7)	87 (100)	
Tribal	3 (50)	3 (50)	6 (100)	
Education of mother				4.355(.360)
Illiterate	2 (40)	3 (60)	5(100)	
Upto primary	25 (71.4)	10 (28.6)	35(100)	
Upto secondary	26 (68.4)	12 (31.6)	38(100)	
Up to higher secondary	9 (90)	1 (10)	10(100)	
Graduate & above	3 (60)	2 (40)	5(100)	
Parity of mother				0.606(.436)
Primipara	46 (67.6)	22 (32.4)	68(100)	
Multipara	19 (76)	6 (24)	25(100)	
Socio economic status				7.633(.106)
BG Prasad cat-I	11 (73.3)	4 (26.7)	15(100)	
BG Prasad cat-II	20 (87)	3 (13)	23(100)	
BG Prasad cat-III	18 (62.1)	11 (37.9)	29(100)	
BG Prasad cat-IV	10 (52.6)	9 (47.4)	19(100)	
BG Prasad cat-V	6 (85.7)	1 (14.3)	7(100)	
Place of delivery				0.052(.820)
Home	3 (75)	1 (25)	4(100)	
Institutional	62(69.7)	27 (30.3)	89(100)	
Age gap between previous two children				1.685(.640)
<1year	1 (50)	1 (50)	2(100)	
<2year	3 (100)	0 (0.0)	3(100)	

<3year	11 (68.8)	5 (31.2)	16(100)	
>3year	50 (69.4)	22 (30.6)	72(100)	
N/A	65 (69.9)	28 (30.1)	93(100)	
Type of delivery				
Term	57 (69.5)	25 (30.5)	82(100)	.063(.969)
Preterm	3 (75)	1 (25)	4(100)	
Post term	5 (71.4)	2 (28.6)	7(100)	
Mode of delivery				
Normal vaginal delivery	34 (65.4)	18 (34.6)	52(100)	1.429(.489)
LSCS	30 (75)	10 (25)	40(100)	
Assisted(forceps)	1 (100)	0 (0.0)	1(100)	

Discussion

Breast feeding is the normal way of feeding infants in all traditional societies. Lactation is a naturally occurring phenomenon following child birth but the act of breast feeding has been complicated by numerous social and cultural factors. For successful breast feeding, mother needs support from all stake holders, including her husband, family, community, the state and the country.

This cross-sectional study was done to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice of breastfeeding among mothers with children aged less than 5 years. A total of 186 mothers, 93 each from Dukli (urban) and Madhupur (rural) were selected based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Socio-demographic characteristics and obstetrical factors were presented in a cross-tabulation. Qualitative data was used in assessing mother's level of understanding, reactions and practice in relation to the concept being studied.

Knowledge about Breast Feeding:

The present study showed, 66.7% participants had good knowledge about breastfeeding in both urban and rural population which is consistent with similar studies conducted by Tampah- Naah and Kumi-Kyereme in Ghana,2013 [13], Vijayalakshmi P, Susheela T and Mythili D in Punjab [14], Bhattacharjya H, Das S, Mog C, Bhowmik S in Tripura [15], Ekambaram M, Bhat V, Ahamed M in Puducherry [16], Tadele N in Ethiopia [17], Akinyinka M in Nigeria [18] where majority of the participants had good knowledge of breast feeding.

Our study showed a significant association between maternal age and the knowledge of exclusive breastfeeding which is consistent with the work by Fosu-Brefo& Arthur [19] in Ghana, 2015. Majority of mothers aged less than 20 years of age showed prominent level of understanding about the essence of breastfeeding an infant. For instance, its role in protecting an infant from diseases, an ideal source of nutrients and it's health benefits on lactating mothers, unlike the results from the study by Mohammed et al. (2014), where mothers' age did not have much influence on the knowledge and practice of exclusive breastfeeding and almost all

mothers irrespective of their age at the time of giving birth were familiar with the concept [20] Present study showed that majority of mothers especially the highly-educated mothers had a good knowledge about the meaning of exclusive breastfeeding which is similar to other studies (Akinyinka et al in Nigeria, 2011 [21], Fosu-Brefo& Arthur in Ghana, 2015 [19], Akinyinka et al 2016 [21]. Mohammed et al. also found a significant relationship between maternal education and the knowledge in exclusive breastfeeding in Egypt in 2014 [20].

Practice of Breastfeeding:

Present study showed, majority of the participant had good practice of breastfeeding. In contrast to our study findings, practice of breastfeeding was low despite the widespread campaigns about exclusive breastfeeding in other studies done by Zhang J et al 2015 [22], Tewabe et al in 2017 [23] in China. Zhang et al 2015 found 55.8% practice of exclusive breastfeeding till the sixth month, which was quite low compared to awareness in exclusive breastfeeding (92.4%) [22]. Similarly, a study by Dun-Dery & Laar in Ghana, 2016 showed that 91 % of participants knew about exclusive breastfeeding, but 10.3 % of them fed their child with only breast milk till the sixth month [24]. In the study conducted by Vijayalakshmi P, Susheela T and Mythili D in Punjab [14], majority (88.5%) of the mothers were breast feeding their infants. While, 85.2% of the mothers were aware of EBF, merely 27% were exclusive breast feeders. In our present study, good breast feeding practice was higher among the age group of 20-30 years but good knowledge was found to be more prevalent in mothers aged less than 20 years of age. Similar finding has been reported in many other studies by Michaelsen K.F., Laren P.S. in Copanhagen [25], Scott J.A., Atkin I. in Perth, Australia [26] and Narayan S., Natarajan N. in India [27].

There is an association between the religion and tribe of mothers with good practice of breastfeeding where Hindus and non-tribal mothers had good breastfeeding practices. We also found a positive association between breast feeding and maternal education status similar to a few other

studies by Wen L.M., Baur L.A. in Sydney, Australia [28] and by Feinstein J.M., Gruszka M.E [29]. Similarly, in our study higher socio economic status co-related with better breastfeeding practices which could be because of the educational status of the mothers from higher socio economic class, which is also in line with the study conducted by Ekambaram M., Bhatt V and Ahamed M. in Puducherry where 65.2 % of the mothers with per capita income more than Rs. 1,500 were graduates [16]. In the present study, majority of the mothers having term and institutional deliveries and those who had undergone LSCS had better practices than those with preterm, house and normal vaginal deliveries, respectively, similar to a study conducted in India in 2000 by Anandaiah R. and Choe M.K. [30] which showed that those mothers who had delivered in a medical facility had positive effects on breast feeding practices.

In the present study sample, breastfeeding counselling, socio economic status, literacy and age of the mother had a significant influence on breastfeeding patterns and breastfeeding knowledge.

Conclusion

The present study on breastfeeding showed approximately two third of the study population had good knowledge on breastfeeding. Majority of the mothers had good practice of breastfeeding. Educated mothers had more good practice than illiterate mothers. Mothers of urban area had more positive attitude towards breastfeeding compared to mothers of rural area. Health education by intense IEC (Information Education Communication) activities about importance of exclusive breastfeeding can enhance knowledge, attitude and practice of breastfeeding among both urban and rural population.

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